

Application of De-Laval Nozzle Transonic Flow Field Computation Approaches

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Abstract : A supersonic expansion cannot be achieved within a convergent-divergent nozzle if the flow velocity does not reach that of the sound at the throat. The computation of the flow field characteristics at the throat is thus essential to the nozzle developed thrust value and therefore to the aircraft or rocket it propels. Several approaches were developed in order to describe the transonic expansion, which takes place through the throat of a De-Laval convergent-divergent nozzle. They all allow reaching good results but show a major shortcoming represented by their inability to describe the transonic flow field for nozzles having a small throat radius. One interesting approach uses velocity series development in terms of the normalized throat radius added to unity instead of solely the normalized throat radius or the traditional small disturbances theory approach. The present investigation carries out the application of three of these approaches for different throat radiuses of curvature. The method using the normalized throat radius added to unity shows better results when applied to geometries integrating small throat radiuses.

Keywords : De-Laval nozzles, transonic calculations, transonic flow, supersonic nozzle

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